

Estimation in the multinomial reencounter model – Where do migrating animals go and how do they survive in their destination area?

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ABSTRACT

Spatial variation in survival has individual fitness consequences and influences population dynamics. Which space animals use during the annual cycle determines how they are affected by this spatial variability. Therefore, knowing spatial patterns of survival and space use is crucial to understand demography of migrating animals. Extracting information on survival and space use from observation data, in particular dead recovery data, requires explicitly identifying the observation process.

We build a fully stochastic model for animals marked in populations of origin, which were found dead in spatially discrete destination areas. The model acts on the population level and includes parameters for use of space, survival and recovery probability. It is based on the division coefficient and the multinomial reencounter model. We use a likelihood-based approach, derive Restricted Maximum Likelihood-like estimates for all parameters and prove their existence and uniqueness.

In a simulation study we demonstrate the performance of the model by using Bayesian estimators derived by the Markov chain Monte Carlo method. We obtain unbiased estimates for survival and recovery probability if the sample size is large enough. Moreover, we apply the model to real-world data of European robins *Erithacus rubecula* ringed at a stopover site. We obtain annual survival estimates for different spatially discrete non-breeding areas. Additionally, we can reproduce already known patterns of use of space for this species.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Seasonal migration, use of space and survival

Spatio-temporal varying demographic parameters are highly relevant for understanding the demography and evolution of species using space on a broader scale, e.g., migratory species (Alerstam et al., 2003). When individuals move in space, they experience changing conditions with consequences for their survival and reproductive success, which finally define their fitness (Hoye et al., 2012). All conditions acting on an individual level have consequences on the population level because individual behavior determines population dynamics, gene flow, community dynamics, ecosystem functions and transmission of parasites and diseases (Bauer et al., 2016).

How spatio-temporal heterogeneous survival affects population dynamics is co-determined by space use. In migratory animals,

individuals differ in which space they use during the annual cycle (Harrison et al., 2011). While individuals of one population of origin may use different migration routes and destination areas, individuals of different populations of origin may share the migration route as well as the destination area. This spatial linkage over time is called migratory connectivity (Webster et al., 2002; Marra et al., 2018). Migratory connectivity has two main components (Finch et al., 2017): the spread of the population of origin, when leaving the area of origin, and the inter-population mixing in the destination area. The effect of spatio-temporal varying survival on population dynamics, therefore, is modulated by migratory connectivity.

Simultaneously, spatio-temporal varying survival influences migratory connectivity. The spatio-temporal varying nature of survival has two dimensions: In the temporal dimension, survival probability differs between different phases of the life or between seasons. In the spatial dimension, survival is affected by spatially varying resources and abiotic and biotic environmental conditions in the habitats used throughout the annual cycle (Gaillard et al., 2010). Examples are spatially heterogeneously allocated food (Suhonen et al., 1992), shelter (Ruczyński et al., 2005), pathogens (Fallon et al., 2006) or mortality risk (Schaub, 2012). The scale of

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both the temporal and the spatial dimension depend on the ecology and behavior of the species under study, the investigated problem and the availability of data.

According to [Nathan et al. \(2008\)](#) research in movement ecology rarely addresses spatio-temporal variation in survival, especially in the context of seasonal migration. Nevertheless, some studies show a relationship between heterogeneous survival on different migration routes and population decline, e.g., in cuckoos ([Hewson et al., 2016](#)) or smolts ([Healy et al., 2017](#)).

Here, we present a mathematically explicit formulation of a modeling framework which enables simultaneously estimating migratory connectivity and survival in the destination area. We use data of animals which are individually marked. When they die, they may be found by humans, who report the code to the institutions managing recovery databases ([Feu et al., 2016](#)). The records of these dead marked animals are called dead recovery data. Applying our model to dead recovery data of marked individuals can reveal the proportion of individuals of a given population of origin migrating to different destination areas (i.e., migratory connectivity) and how well individuals survive in different parts of the complete destination space of the population or the species under study. The mathematically explicit formulation enables us to assess parameter identifiability and serves as a basis for further model development. This may support further research in the field of movement ecology and demography.

1.2. Observing the pattern created by survival and use of space

Parameters reflecting survival and migratory connectivity can be separately estimated from the observation data ([Rushing et al., 2021](#)). This is because the observation data describes how individuals from a specific population are distributed in space over time. This spatio-temporal distribution is shaped by both survival and migratory connectivity, which are the unknown demographic traits of the population. The impact of survival on the spatio-temporal distribution is different to that of migratory connectivity ([Fletcher et al., 2019](#)). Namely, survival shapes the distribution of ages at death, whereas migratory connectivity has no influence on this. Therefore, it is possible to disentangle both parameters.

Inferring directly from the observation data to survival and migratory connectivity nearly always leads to biased results because some groups of animals are observed disproportionately often ([Korner-Nievergelt et al., 2010](#); [Thorup et al., 2014](#); [Rotellam et al., 2000](#); [Stevens et al., 2011](#); [Zurell et al., 2010](#); [Cohen et al., 2014](#)). More available observers and less required effort increases the likelihood of observation. Coincidentally, many observable individuals and conspicuous species or marks minimize observation effort. Therefore, just as survival and use of space, the observation process is a spatio-temporal process in and of itself. For example, several studies describe heterogeneous recovery probability for dead animals across space, time, and categorical variables like different countries ([Robinson et al., 2009](#); [McCulloch et al., 1992](#); [Sales, 1973](#); [Korner-Nievergelt et al., 2010](#)). Survival and use of space determine simultaneously if animals are available for observation. This means, an animal can be observed at a given geographical point only if it used this point and if it died there. The higher space use and the lower survival probability, the more animals will be observed. Both biological processes interact with the observation process in a way highly depending on the type of data generated by the chosen observation method. The issue arising from the so-called observer bias can be solved by explicitly modeling the observation process as proposed in the citations above. For example, [Cohen et al. \(2014\)](#) estimated the observation probability by adding the region-specific observation effort as a spatially varying covariate to the observation probability.

To facilitate model development, we focus on mark-dead recovery data, a singular data source with information on survival and migratory connectivity. On the one hand, finding individuals at death leads to a very precise information on survival ([Kendall et al., 2006](#)), since the lifespan is known if marks are applied at a known age. On the other hand, the data of one individual provides only little information, especially on use of space. But pooling the data points of many individuals can give a good overview of use of space and mean survival on a population level ([Thorup et al., 2014](#); [Baillie et al., 2009](#); [McGarvey and Feenstra, 2002](#); [Prévo and Licoppe, 2013](#)). The cheap and light markings, which can be applied to many individuals of a certain group of animals, often enable achieving a high population coverage. The data then consists of the counts of individuals marked in distinct populations of origin which died in different destination areas, where their carcass was found and reported. This data tends to be sparse (but see [Frederiksen et al., 2018](#)) and therefore challenging to analyze, but huge databases with such data are available that are historically valuable (e.g., EURING data base of recovered marked birds since 1901, [Feu et al., 2016](#)).

1.3. Multinomially modeling survival, space use and the observation process

Collecting a sample of independent and identically distributed life histories results in the multinomial distribution of the vector of counts for every possible life history. The life histories are independent, when they are mutually exclusive, meaning that each marked individual has exactly one life history or recovery history. The assumption of independent and identically distributed life histories is true for live capture-recaptures (Cormack-Jolly-Seber models: [Cormack, 1964](#); [Seber, 1965](#); [Jolly, 1965](#)), dead-recoveries (Seber models: [Fordham and Cormack, 1970](#); [Seber, 1971](#)), multi-state models, when the states are mutually exclusive ([Gauthier and Lebreton, 2008](#)), and even multi-state reencounter or recapture models with imperfect detection, when the probability of an imperfect detection is explicitly formulated ([Conn and Cooch, 2009](#)). The number of individuals marked and never recovered again, provides crucial information for estimating recovery probability, and, therefore, these individuals belong to the dataset.

The multinomial reencounter model ([Thorup and Conn, 2009](#); [Bauthian et al., 2007](#); [Korner-Nievergelt et al., 2010](#)) is a generalization of a special case of a multi-state reencounter model. It is a special case because the transition matrix between states is the identity matrix and the parameter survival does not vary between age classes. The generalization is that the multinomial reencounter model integrates several multi-state reencounter models by means of the parameter migratory connectivity. The parameter migratory connectivity is a transition matrix from the area of origin to the destination area, in which every row sums up to one. Every row contains the proportion of individuals of one area of origin going to a specific destination area. As a result, the migratory connectivity model is a multinomial model in itself, so that the multinomial reencounter model is a composition of two multinomial processes. The integration of data from different populations with shared and not shared parameters makes the parameters identifiable.

[Busse \(1981\)](#) and [Kania and Busse \(1987\)](#) estimate the number of individuals migrating from different populations of origin to specific destination areas by solving a system of linear equations using least-square methods. In addition to this approach, we provide formulae for the parameter estimation also for more than two destination areas, mainly using the characteristics of the determinant of a matrix. We include survival as a parameter in the approach of Busse and Kania and provide an estimator for it. Moreover, we embed it in a likelihood-based approach. The formulation of the likelihood and including survival traces back to the

work of the multinomial reencounter model (Thorup and Conn, 2009; Bauthian et al., 2007; Korner-Nievergelt et al., 2010).

We refine the multinomial reencounter model by explicitly using a truncated geometric distribution to prevent observation times (duration of the study, i.e., maximum possible age that can be observed due to limited observation time) shorter than the possible age from biasing the survival estimator. In addition to that, we derive Restricted Maximum Likelihood (REML)-like estimates for all parameters and prove their existence and uniqueness. This is possible by partitioning the likelihood and stepwise estimating the parameters using the characteristics of the multinomial distribution. The procedure traces back to the REML approach (Patterson and Thompson, 1971; Harville, 1977).

2. Method

2.1. The multinomial reencounter model

We build a fully stochastic model for individuals marked in spatially discrete areas of origin $\mathcal{B} = \{1, \dots, b, \dots, B\}$ and seasonally migrating to a destination area $\mathcal{W} = \{1, \dots, w, \dots, W\}$. The model is very general and can be used for every two types of area: depending on the species areas of origin can be, e.g., breeding areas or stopover sites and destination areas can be, e.g., wintering areas or moult areas. The number of destination areas must be less or equal to the number of areas of origin. Dead recoveries always take place in the spatially discrete destination areas. Therefore, the destination area may spatially overlap with the area of origin, when animals die at or in the vicinity of the marking location. The age at death is a discrete time step t within the observation period $\mathcal{T} = \{1, \dots, t, \dots, T\}$, where T is the observation time. Every marked individual originating from an area of origin has the feature to go to a specific destination area and to die at a specific age. The model does not consider the individual but the population level. Therefore, all individuals with equal features are summed to the number of marked individuals N_{bwt} from area of origin b , going to destination area w and dying at age t . A dot in the index indicates a sum over a specific index, e.g., $N_{b\cdot} := \sum_{w \in \mathcal{W}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} N_{bwt}$. Because only the number of marked individuals in an area of origin $N_{b\cdot}$ can be observed, only $N_{b\cdot}$ (and hence N_{\dots}) are directly observable. All other counts, including N_{bwt} , are latent variables. The count of marked individuals may also be written as a vector

$$\mathbf{N} = \begin{pmatrix} N_{1\cdot} \\ N_{2\cdot} \\ \vdots \\ N_{B\cdot} \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{N}_{>0}^B. \quad \mathbb{N}_{>0} \text{ denotes all positive integers excluding zero, and } \mathbb{N}_{\geq 0} \text{ denotes all non-negative integers including zero.}$$

The latent count of marked individuals in the destination area w

$$\text{may also be written as the vector } \mathbf{N}_w = \begin{pmatrix} N_{1w} \\ N_{2w} \\ \vdots \\ N_{Bw} \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 0}^B. \text{ Analo-}$$

gously, we write the count of dead recoveries $y_{bwt} \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 0}$ from an area of origin b in a destination area w at time step t and indicate a sum over an index by a dot. For example, $y_{\cdot wt} := \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} y_{bwt}$. As y_{bwt} can be observed directly, all sums can also be observed directly. The count of dead recoveries may also be written as a matrix

$$\mathbf{Y} = (\mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{y}_2, \dots, \mathbf{y}_W) \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 0}^{B \times W} \text{ where } \mathbf{y}_w = \begin{pmatrix} y_{1w} \\ y_{2w} \\ \vdots \\ y_{Bw} \end{pmatrix} \text{ for all } w \in \mathcal{W}.$$

The count of dead recoveries and marked individuals can be combined in the matrices $\mathbf{Y}_w^{(N)} = (y_1, \dots, y_{w-1}, \mathbf{N}, y_{w+1}, \dots, y_W) \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 0}^{B \times W}$.

The model describes the following scenario. From the overall number of marked individuals N_{\dots} , the proportion of marked individuals n_b belongs to the population of origin b . Individuals of the same population of origin b migrate in different proportions $m_{bw} \in (0, 1)$ to different destination areas w , whereas individuals of different populations of origin migrate to the same destination area. For the proportion of every area of origin $b \in \mathcal{B}$, it is valid that $\sum_{w \in \mathcal{W}} m_{bw} = 1$. After arriving in a specific destination area, the conditions for all individuals are the same. They survive year by year with a certain survival probability $s_w \in (0, 1)$ until they die with the inverse probability $1 - s_w$. Some dead individuals are found and reported with the recovery probability $r_w \in (0, 1)$. The dead recoveries are a representative subset of the investigated populations and uncertainties in the data generating process, e.g., wrongly assigned marks, are not modeled.

The model parameters annual survival, migratory connectivity and recovery probability are independent of each other. They do not exhibit temporal or spatial autocorrelation. All parameters are constant over time. Additionally, annual survival does not vary between age classes. It follows the Markov property, so surviving to the next year only depends on being alive in the current year. Moreover, neither survival nor recovery probability depend on the areas from which individuals originate. Individuals show site fidelity to both areas of origin and destination areas. Therefore, migratory connectivity does not change between years. Further, we assume that no individuals migrate to areas not covered in the study. Finally, for mathematical reasons only, the number of populations of origin is greater or equal than the number of destination areas and no two populations of origin show the same migratory connectivity distribution.

2.2. Prerequisites

The individual animals sharing a life history are independent, identically distributed. The dead-recovery data Y are tuples $Y = \{(y_{bwt} : t \in \mathcal{T}) N_{bwt} - y_{bwt} : b \in \mathcal{B}, w \in \mathcal{W}\}$.

Y is multinomially distributed (e.g., Agresti, 2003, p. 6):

$$Y \sim \text{Multin}(N_{\dots}, \{p_{bw} : b \in \mathcal{B}, w \in \mathcal{W}\}), \quad (1)$$

where

$$p_{bw}(Y_{bw}) = (\{n_b m_{bw} s_w^{t-1} (1 - s_w) r_w : t \in \mathcal{T}\} (n_b m_{bw} - n_b m_{bw} (1 - s_w^T) r_w)). \quad (2)$$

Therefore, the parameters survival, migratory connectivity and recovery probability of the distribution can be estimated using some properties of the multinomial distribution.

Firstly, for each combination of $b \in \mathcal{B}$ and $w \in \mathcal{W}$ the maximum likelihood estimator (MLE) of a multinomial distribution (e.g., Agresti, 2003, p. 22) is

$$p_{bw} = Y_{bw} / N_{\dots}$$

So, the MLE for p_{bw} only estimates the product of all parameters (see Eq. (2)). To obtain estimates of the separate parameters, we develop a stepwise procedure using an approach similar to the REML-like approach. The REML approach goes back to Patterson and Thompson (1971) and Harville (1977). We assume in our REML-like approach that partial information provided by the data may suffice to estimate each parameter. More specifically, the likelihood can be partitioned in several likelihoods. If one partition contains only one unknown parameter, the unknown parameter can be estimated using the MLE. In a next step another unknown parameter can be estimated by plugging in the already estimated parameter in another partial likelihood containing only these two

parameters. These steps can be iterated until all parameters are estimated. In this study, partitioning the likelihood is based on the properties of the multinomial distribution.

The multinomial distribution can be preserved under certain transformations. If several classes of multinomial data are aggregated to one class, the data of the aggregated classes is still multinomially distributed (e.g., Ross, 2009, Problem 6.4, pp. 294+493). The count parameter remains the same as in the original multinomial distribution. In contrast, the probability parameter of the aggregated class becomes the sum of the probabilities of the original classes. For example, the variable of interest is the place but not the exact time step of a dead recovery. So, for every destination area, the data of all time steps can be aggregated.

The data will also remain multinomially distributed when conditioning on specific classes only (e.g., Ross, 2009, exercise 4c, p. 265). Thereby, the count parameter will be the sum over all considered classes. The probability of one class is the original probability normalized by the sum over the probabilities of all considered classes. For example, conditioned probabilities enables only regarding the class of found individuals while ignoring all not recovered individuals.

The marginal distribution of the multinomial distribution is the binomial distribution. Both have the same count parameter and the probability parameter is the multinomial probability conditioned on the considered class.

If aggregating or conditioning multinomial data gives rise to, e.g., infinite geometric series or partial sums of geometric series, this may simplify terms and enable maximum likelihood estimation of the separate parameters in a REML-like approach as shown below. Survival and the latent number of individuals of an area of origin in a destination area N_{bw} are independently estimated directly from the data. Then, estimating migratory connectivity needs a plug-in of the already estimated N_{bw} . Finally, recovery probability can be estimated by plugging in the already estimated survival and N_{bw} .

2.3. Parameter estimation

Survival. Aggregating and conditioning the dead recovery data from Eq. (1) reveals that the time steps of the dead recovery data are distributed in the following way:

$$t_w \sim Geo^{tr}(1 - s_w, T), \tag{4}$$

where Geo^{tr} denotes the geometric distribution truncated at the end of the observation period T .

As survival is the parameter of the truncated geometric distribution, it can be estimated by the MLE. The formula is:

$$\hat{s}_w = \underset{s_w \in (0,1)}{\operatorname{argmax}} \left(\sum_{t=1}^T (y_{.wt})((t-1) \log s_w + \log(1-s_w) - \log(1-s_w^t)) \right). \tag{5}$$

We call Eq. (5) the REML-like estimator of survival. For the proof of the Eqs. (4) and (5), see A.

The value taken by the MLE \hat{s}_w is unique under the condition that

$$\sum_t y_{.wt}(t-1) + y_{.w}(1-T)/2 < 0. \tag{6}$$

If not, $\hat{s}_w = 1$. For the proof of this, see B.

The condition in Eq. (6) is at least fulfilled if the data is monotonically decreasing in $t, T > 1$ for every destination area (for the proof, see C). The larger the sample size, the more likely the data will be monotonically decreasing (for the proof, see D).

The MLE \hat{s}_w will also be unique if the observation time is large enough. Then, the data is not truncated and a geometric distribu-

tion without truncation has always a unique MLE (for the proof, see E).

The latent count N_{bw} . The latent count N_{bw} is the count of individuals marked in an area of origin having the feature to go to a specific destination area w . It can be estimated uniquely by the data of dead recoveries in all destination areas. This quantity is essential to estimate migratory connectivity and recovery probability.

Aggregating all dead recoveries of an area of origin found in a destination area over all time steps leads to a binomially distributed variable:

$$y_{bw} \sim Bin(N_{bw}, (1 - s_w^T)r_w). \tag{7}$$

According to the estimate for the parameter of a binomial distribution describing the number of trials given by Feldman and Fox (1968), the latent count N_{bw} is just a multiple $\lambda_w \in \mathbb{R}$ of the dead recoveries summed over all time steps:

$$\hat{N}_{bw} = \lfloor \lambda_w y_{bw} \rfloor. \tag{8}$$

For the proof, see F.

In this case the scaling factor in Eq. (8) is for squared matrices $\mathbf{Y}_w^{(N)}$ and \mathbf{Y}

$$\lambda_w = \det \mathbf{Y}_w^{(N)} / \det \mathbf{Y}. \tag{9}$$

For the proof, see G. Because of the definition of the determinant, the scaling factor (Eq. (9)) can only be given for squared matrices. If the number of areas of origin exceeds the number of destination areas $\mathbf{Y}_w^{(N)}$, the matrix has more rows than columns. Nevertheless, the matrix can be converted to a squared matrix without loss of information. There are several possibilities how to do this. We decided to aggregate the last rows, allowing to use all data available. Thereby, we obtain the matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{Y}} = (\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_1, \tilde{\mathbf{y}}_2, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{y}}_W)$, where $\tilde{\mathbf{Y}} \in \mathbb{N}^{W \times W}$ and

$$\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_w = \begin{pmatrix} y_{1w} \\ y_{2w} \\ \vdots \\ y_{W-1w} \\ \sum_{b=W}^W y_{bw} \end{pmatrix}, \tilde{\mathbf{y}}_w \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 0}^W.$$

Which areas of origin to aggregate can be arbitrarily chosen because the parameters of interest only depend on the destination areas.

Migratory connectivity. The latent count is multinomially distributed with migratory connectivity as parameter

$$\{N_{bw} : w \in \mathcal{W}\} \sim Multin(N_{b..}, \{m_{bw} : w \in \mathcal{W}\}). \tag{10}$$

The MLE for the proportion of individuals from the population of origin b going to the destination area w is

$$\hat{m}_{bw} = y_{bw} \cdot \det \mathbf{Y}_w^{(N)} / (N_b \cdot \det \mathbf{Y}). \tag{11}$$

Eq. (11) is the REML-like estimator of the migratory connectivity. For the proof, see H.

Recovery probability. From Eq. (7) we know that the dead recoveries of an area of origin found in a destination area aggregated over all time steps is binomially distributed with parameters N_{bw} and $(1 - s_w^T)r_w$. As the probability parameter does not depend on the area of origin, the sum of all recoveries over all areas of origin is also binomially distributed:

$$y_{.w} \sim Bin(N_{.w}, (1 - s_w^T)r_w). \tag{12}$$

By plugging in the estimates for the survival and the latent count, we obtain the REML-like estimator of r as

$$\hat{r}_w = \det \mathbf{Y} / ((1 - \hat{s}_w^T) \det \mathbf{Y}_w^{(N)}). \tag{13}$$

For the proof, see I.

If the observation time is long enough, the influence of the survival estimator vanishes. As $s_w^T \rightarrow 0$ for $T \rightarrow \infty$, so $\hat{r}_w \rightarrow \det \mathbf{Y} / \det \mathbf{Y}_w^{(N)}$ for $T \rightarrow \infty$.

3. Simulation study

3.1. Method

We investigate the performance of the estimators given above in a simulation study. Therefore, we simulate data Y_{sim} from the model for three different scenarios and repeat this a hundred times. The scenarios differ in their observation time of $T \in \{2, 5, 10\}$ years. Every scenario considers 13 areas of origin and 12 destination areas. We use fixed values for survival probability s and recovery probability r . Thereby, every destination area has a unique combination of survival and recovery (see Table 1 for exact values). In contrast, the values for the proportion m_{bw} of individuals of one area of origin going to one destination area and the number of marked individuals per area of origin N_b are chosen randomly for all areas of origin and destination areas in every simulation by the following rule: $N_b \sim Unif(10000, 20000)$.

In every simulation we estimate survival probability, migratory connectivity and recovery probability using a Bayesian estimator. The Bayesian estimation uses Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) simulations in JAGS (Plummer, 2003) with 3 chains and 10000 iterations. We discard the first 8000 iterations, allowing the algorithm to adapt to the data. To avoid problems at the boundaries, we put priors at the logit of the probabilities for recovery and survival. These prior distributions for all $b \in \mathcal{B}$ and all $w \in \mathcal{W}$ are weakly informative: $\log(s_{Bayes,w}/(1 - s_{Bayes,w})) \sim N(0, 10/3)$,

$$\bar{m}_{bw} \sim Unif(0, 1), m_{Bayes,bw} = \bar{m}_{bw} / \sum_{w \in \mathcal{W}} \bar{m}_{bw}, \log(r_{Bayes,w}/(1 - r_{Bayes,w})) \sim N(-1, 25).$$

The likelihood is formulated by the stochastic distributions for the age at death t (Eq. (4)), the latent count N_{bw} of individuals from the area of origin b going to the destination area w (Eq. (10)) and for the count of dead recoveries y_w (Eq. (12)).

Moreover, the theoretical REML-like estimators theoretical \hat{r}_{REML} and theoretical \hat{s}_{REML} are determined by using the expected values of the simulated data $\mathbb{E}Y_{sim}$ as data in the equations for the survival estimator (5) and the recovery estimator (13). Thereby, the bwt -th entry of \mathbf{Y} corresponds to $(\mathbb{E}Y_{sim})_{bwt} = N_b \cdot m_{bw} s_w^{t-1} (1 - s_w) r_w$.

We implement the method described in the method section in the softwares R (R Core Team, 2018) and JAGS (Plummer, 2003). All figures are built with R.

3.2. Results

The theoretical REML-like estimator for survival is unbiased (Fig. 1). If the observation time is adequate for the survival, the Bayesian survival estimate is also unbiased. For high survival probabilities in too short observation times, the Bayesian survival estimator underestimates the true survival. The precision of the Bayesian survival estimator increases with increasing observation time.

Likewise, the theoretical REML-like estimator for the recovery probability is unbiased (Fig. 2). The estimated Bayesian recovery probability is also unbiased, if the observation time is long enough for the given survival values. If survival is higher for a given observation time, but the bias of survival estimates is small, the recovery probability is overestimated. Thereby, the bias of recovery proba-

Table 1
True survival and recovery probability of the 12 destination areas w_1, \dots, w_{12} of the simulation study.

i	1	2	3	4
s_{w_i}	0.10	0.37	0.63	0.90
r_{w_i}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}
i	5	6	7	8
s_{w_i}	0.10	0.37	0.63	0.90
r_{w_i}	4.1×10^{-3}	4.1×10^{-3}	4.1×10^{-3}	4.1×10^{-3}
i	9	10	11	12
s_{w_i}	0.10	0.37	0.63	0.90
r_{w_i}	1.353×10^{-1}	1.353×10^{-1}	1.353×10^{-1}	1.353×10^{-1}

Fig. 1. Bayesian estimate for the survival probability s_{Bayes} plotted against the true survival s (0.1, 0.4, 0.6, 0.9) for different observation times T (left: 2 years, middle: 5 years, right: 10 years) and a constant recovery probability r (4.1×10^{-3}). Each boxplot contains estimates of 100 simulated datasets. As a visual reference true survival s is shown as the grey solid line. The theoretical REML-like estimator s_{REML} is plotted as the black dashed line.

Fig. 2. Bayesian estimate for the recovery probability r_{Bayes} plotted against the true survival s (0.1, 0.4, 0.6, 0.9) for different observation times T (left: 2 years, middle: 5 years, right: 10 years) and a constant recovery probability r (4.1×10^{-3}). Each boxplot contains estimates of 100 simulated datasets. As a visual reference true recovery probability r is shown as the grey solid line. The theoretical REML-like estimator r_{REML} is plotted as the black dashed line.

bility increases with increasing survival probability and decreasing observation time. If survival is so high for a given observation time, that survival is underestimated, the biases of the recovery probability seem to neutralize each other.

The Bayesian estimate of migratory connectivity nearly linearly depends on the true value m (Fig. 3). This relationship is stronger when the recovery probability is higher and when the observation

Fig. 3. Scatterplot illustrating the relationship between true values of the proportion m of individuals going from the area of origin b to the destination area w and the Bayesian estimate \hat{m} . Faceting is done by recovery probability r (columns), observation time T (rows) and survival probability s (shading of dots). Dashed line: perfect linear relationship. Solid line: loess smoother of data. Grey polygon: standard error of loess smoother. Number of simulated datasets: 100 per facet.

time is longer. Survival probability does not influence the estimates of migratory connectivity.

4. Application

4.1. Migratory connectivity and survival of European robins

The European robin *Erithacus rubecula* (robin from now on) is a small 17 g songbird breeding all over Europe. It is a partial migrant. Northern breeding populations consist probably almost exclusively of obligatory migrants. They migrate in fall in southwestern directions to avoid the harsh winters in northern latitudes. Breeding populations in central, western, and southern Europe harbor individuals which may or may not migrate. Breeding birds from Great Britain are mostly residents (Ambrosini et al., 2016). Robins show a leapfrog migration pattern (Korner-Nievergelt et al., 2014); individuals breeding at higher latitudes migrate to lower latitudes. Thereby, they overtake individuals breeding less far in the North, which stay closer to their breeding areas during the non-breeding period. Non-breeding conditions may affect both resident and migrating populations in their migration propensity and distance, but mechanisms remain unclear (Arizaga et al., 2012). We ask, what is the annual survival probability of individuals wintering in different areas in Europe and Northern Africa (see Fig. 4).

4.2. Method

Data. We apply the method described in Section 2 to a dataset of robins gathered at the island Greifswalder Oie in the Baltic Sea 54°15'N 13°55'E, Germany. This dataset contains 98 399 individuals ringed during fall migration from 1994 to 2018. Out of these, in

total, 48 individuals were found dead during the period from November to February of any year after marking until 2018. Migrating robins should have reached their non-breeding areas by November and should not start migrating back to their breeding areas before March. The island is used as a stopover site by robins during migration. Therefore, the breeding area of the individuals is unknown. However, we can assume that individuals with different passage dates have different breeding areas (Korner-Nievergelt et al., 2014; Bauer et al., 2005). Commonly, the earlier individuals start migrating in fall, the further north they breed. Arbitrarily, we define three discrete breeding areas corresponding to early, intermediate and late passage dates by using the 1/3- and 2/3- quantile of individual passage dates, respectively. For example, we assume an individual to migrate early when it belongs to the 1/3 earliest migrating individuals marked on the island over all years. This results in a time span from the 1st August to 23rd September for early passage ($n = 43\,177$), from 24th September to 6th October for intermediate passage ($n = 32\,389$) and from 7th October to 6th November for late passage ($n = 31\,833$). The ringing season, i.e., days with capture effort, truncates the passage dates at the 1st August and the 6th November.

The model estimates survival from the distribution of age at death of the individual. The age at death is reconstructed from the year of marking and the year of recovery. During fall migration robins can be assigned into two age classes, i.e., first-year individuals hatched within the same year and individuals hatched at least in the preceding year (Svensson, 1992). Therefore, the exact year of birth is only known for 37 first-year individuals. The 11 other individuals only have a known minimum age, which we used as the age. This may contain different sources of bias in survival estimation, which should be investigated in detail elsewhere. Nevertheless, we consider all birds for analysis to increase the sample size.

Fig. 4. Location of dead recoveries of robins ringed at different passage dates (circle: early, triangle: intermediate, square: late) during fall migration at the Greifswalder Oie, Northern Germany (arrow). Time of dead recoveries is between November and February. Discrete non-breeding areas are indicated by shading: dark: North, medium: Central, light: South.

We define discrete non-breeding areas roughly by increasing distance to the place of marking. We start by outlining the area where robins ringed on the Greifswalder Oie potentially occur. For that, all locations of alive and dead ring re-encounters of robins marked on the island Greifswalder Oie ($n = 142$) and found during the whole annual cycle are considered. We calculate a buffer of 3.5° around these locations using qGIS (QGIS Development Team, 2021) (see J Fig. J.8). Then we define inside the buffer the discrete non-breeding areas as follows (Fig. 4): The Southern non-breeding area includes parts of Northern Africa and the Iberian Peninsula. The Central non-breeding area contains parts of Great Britain, France, Switzerland, Italy and northwestern parts of the Balkans. The Northern non-breeding area encompasses Belgium, the Netherlands, Germany, Czech Republic, Poland, and Slovakia. Countries further North and East within the buffer (Denmark, Fenno-Scandinavia, Latvia, Lithuania, Estonia, Russia, and Belarus) are also part of the Northern non-breeding area. However, no European robin marked on the island Greifswalder Oie were found there between November and February.

Because robins were ringed every fall between 1994 and 2018, observation time varies between one and 24 years. All except one of the robins were recovered dead one to four years after marking and use an observation period of five years. For technical reasons, we discarded the only older bird reaching an age of at least 16. See the discussion for more details.

Parameter estimation. We estimate survival probability, migratory connectivity and recovery probability using a Bayesian approach implemented in JAGS (Plummer, 2003) similar to the simulation study. We ran three chains with different starting val-

ues to be able to check for convergence both visually and by calculating \hat{R} -values. All \hat{R} -values were less than 1.1. Each chain consisted of 250 000 iterations. We discarded the first 50 000 as the adaptation phase of the algorithm. Moreover, we only kept every 1000th iteration for inference to minimize effects of autocorrelation.

4.3. Results

Raw data. The raw data is presented as a point pattern in Fig. 4. By tendency, early migrating robins were found further south in winter than individuals with intermediate passage dates. Dead recoveries of late migrating robins cluster more in the northern non-breeding area.

Migratory connectivity. The Bayesian estimates of the proportion of robins wintering in the three discrete non-breeding areas \hat{m} fit the pattern indicated by visual inspection of the raw data (Fig. 5). 50.6% (0.95-CrI: 22.0–79.2 %) of early passing birds go to the South, 37 % (0.95-CrI: 8.7–69.8 %) to the Central and 12.4 % (0.95-CrI: 1.4–34.2 %) stay in the northern non-breeding area. A majority of 61.7 % (0.95-CrI: 12.4–93.9 %) of the individuals with intermediate passage dates migrate to the Central, whereas 16.7% (0.95-CrI: 2.6–57.2 %) go to the South and another 21.5 % (0.95-CrI: 1.3–59.0 %) stay in the northern non-breeding area. 40.2 % (0.95-CrI: 11.0–74.0 %) of the late passing birds stay in the North, 42.3 % (0.95-CrI: 12.2–76.5 %) winter in the Central and only around 17.5% (0.95-CrI: 4.1–38.0 %) migrate to the southern non-breeding area.

Fig. 5. Boxplots of Bayesian estimates of the proportion of robins from early (left), intermediate (middle) and late (right) passage dates to the non-breeding area South (light), Central (medium) or North (dark).

Fig. 6. Boxplots of Bayesian estimates of the survival of robins in the non-breeding areas South, Central or North.

Survival. The estimates of the survival probability (Fig. 6) of robins staying in the central and the southern non-breeding area are equal with 38.8% (0.95-CrI: 21.0–61.6 %) and 39.0 % (0.95-CrI: 18.2–65.8 %), respectively. The northern non-breeding area displays the lowest survival with 29 % (0.95-CrI: 12.7–49.5 %).

Recovery probability. The recovery probability is low in all non-breeding areas (Fig. 7). The recovery probability for the northern area is 0.104% (0.95-CrI: 0.029–0.311 %). For the central and southern area, it is only half of the one of the northern area with 0.050% (0.95-CrI: 0.019–0.148 %) and 0.055% (0.95-CrI: 0.020–0.127 %), respectively.

Due to the low sample size of 48 dead recoveries, all estimates have a large 95% credible interval and some Markov chains produce outliers as seen in the boxplots.

5. Discussion

5.1. Model and parameter estimation

Relevance of the model and our contribution. The multinomial reencounter model is relevant because it enables to estimate spatially varying survival. Within the temporal dimensions of migration, survival should significantly affect individual behavior and demography. Likewise, in the spatial scale of migration, spatial variance in survival and the observation process is important. Thus, it is essential to explicitly model annual survival to obtain meaningful estimates for use of space.

Several studies use the multinomial reencounter model (Korner-Nievergelt et al., 2010; Bauthian et al., 2007; Procházka et al., 2017; Marx et al., 2016) and enhanced versions of the model using much richer data than the data used in the current paper (Frederiksen et al., 2018). To our knowledge, this is the first time that area-specific survival is estimated for discrete destination areas in the context of the multinomial reencounter model. Nevertheless, Rushing et al. (2021) estimated area-specific survival, migratory connectivity and recovery probability in an integrated approach of telemetry and capture-recapture data. Moreover, we provide formulae for the theoretical REML-like estimates resembling the behavior of the Bayesian estimates of the multinomial reencounter model. Thereby, we enhance the explicit estimates of Busse (1981) and Kania and Busse (1987) from two to a finite number of areas of origin. The REML-like estimates are much faster to evaluate than simulation studies, e.g., if one wants to investigate how violating model assumptions would influence the estimators.

Parameter estimation. Estimating survival, migratory connectivity and recovery probability uniquely is possible mainly for two reasons. Survival and the latent count of individuals from an area of origin going to a destination area is estimated independently of each other. On the one hand, survival uses only the information of age at death from the data. On the other hand, the latent count uses only the spatial information. The latent count is estimable because the information of all the different areas of origin is available, including the partial information of the not found individuals. But the latent count carries information on the migratory connectivity, which only depends on one area of origin. Disentangling

Fig. 7. Boxplots of Bayesian estimates of the recovery probability of robins in the non-breeding areas South, Central or North.

migratory connectivity and recovery probability is possible because the fate in the destination area is independent of the area of origin. The recovery probability only depends on the destination area, while migratory connectivity depends on both the area of origin and the destination area.

5.2. Simulation study

The simulation study highlights that an adequate observation time enables unbiased parameter estimates. The practical application of REML-like estimators is limited. Even minor changes in the data from the true distribution, e.g., due to small sample size leads to estimators which do not fulfil the criteria of probability or density. Therefore, we recommend the Bayesian estimators for analyzing real-world data. Nevertheless, the REML-like estimators may help to investigate the behavior of Bayesian estimators, e.g., when the data violates model assumptions. This can be done by visually inspecting the theoretical formulae of REML-like estimators and is computationally much faster than MCMC-simulations for the Bayesian estimator itself.

5.3. Application

The results on migratory connectivity match with the already described leapfrog migration pattern. Under the assumption that earlier migrating birds originate from farther North (Korner-Nievergelt et al., 2014), more Northern breeding birds winter further South, so that they have to "jump" over the more Southern breeding birds. Regarding survival map and migratory connectivity

estimates simultaneously, early and intermediate passing individuals seem to winter mainly in the areas where robins survive best. The analysis does not change the picture of migratory connectivity, which we already expect by looking at the raw data. But it extracts additional information on survival probability from the data, which is not visible by investigating the raw data visually.

Survival estimates between 30 % and 40 % lie in the already known order of magnitude for robins (e.g., Siriwardena et al., 1998). The geometric distribution assumes that every age class has the same annual survival probability. This assumption may be true for the robins' dataset, as all robins are already on migration. For example, Gruebler et al. (2014) report equal non-breeding survival for juvenile and adult barn swallows *Hirundo rustica* when only juveniles are considered, which already left the breeding area.

The model fit can be improved manually, when the upper tail of the geometric distribution are too light. With higher age classes data becomes sparser, so that counts for some of these age classes may become zero by chance and forces the upper tail of the geometric distribution to be lighter. In this case the geometric distribution may have a better fit to the data when higher age classes are discarded by shortening the observation time. For example, we estimated survival in the robins' dataset by discarding one individual, dying at the age of 16. Retaining this individual would lead to zero counts for the ages five to 15. This is most likely a random effect of the small sample size of 48. Treating these counts as true zeros decreases the survival estimate to unrealistically low values. Further developments of the method described here should involve an approach to directly deal with such zeros circumventing the slightly arbitrary choice of observation time for such cases.

5.4. Conclusion

In this study, we described a statistical mark-recovery model that allows disentangling migratory connectivity from spatially heterogeneous survival and spatially heterogeneous recovery probability. It may be used for identifying areas of high mortality risk for migratory species or for understanding the evolution of different migration patterns. Moreover, it can form the basis of analyses aiming to link conditions in destination areas to population trends observed in the areas of origin or vice versa.

The model contains many simplifying assumptions. Especially, choosing discrete destination areas is arbitrary. Nevertheless, if partitioning thoroughly, this model may give valid results even for small datasets. Care must be taken if data is sparse and, e.g., some areas do not contain any observations.

Possible enhancements. Defining a continuous destination space may be a worthy enhancement. Survival could also be estimated by a more complex model than the truncated geometric distribution. This would also allow for estimating age-specific survival, like infant mortality and senescence. Other enhancements would be to investigate if relaxing site fidelity or including varying survival across the annual cycle (Marra et al., 2015; Rushing et al., 2017) and carry-over effects (Catry et al., 2013; O'Connor et al., 2014) would still lead to identifiable parameters. Such carry-over effects are likely to be common (Harrison et al., 2011) but as a consequence of their correlated structure they are difficult to identify. Substituting the simple observation process by a more complex one enables integrating more data sources and data sources with other quality such as tracking data and thereby increases information.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Saskia Schirmer: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing - original draft. **Fränzi Korner-Nievergelt:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing - review & editing. **Jan A. C. von Rönne:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Data curation, Visualization, Writing - review & editing. **Volkmar Liebscher:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing - review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Distribution of time steps and maximum likelihood estimator of survival

Theorem 1. The ages at death t_w in a destination area w of the dead recoveries in Eq. (1) are distributed in the following way:

$$t_w \sim Geo^{tr}(1 - s_w, T),$$

where Geo^{tr} denotes the geometric distribution truncated at the end of the observation period T . The MLE for s_w is

$$\hat{s}_w = \underset{s_w \in (0,1)}{\operatorname{argmax}} \left(\sum_{w,t} (y_{wt}) ((t-1) \log s_w + \log(1-s_w) - \log(1-s_w^t)) \right).$$

Proof. Firstly, we consider all destination areas separately from each other. By conditioning the data in Eq. (1) on a specific destination area w , we receive for all $w \in \mathcal{W}$

$$\begin{aligned} & (\{y_{bwt} : b \in \mathcal{B}, t \in \mathcal{T}\} | N_w - y_w) \\ & \sim \operatorname{Multin} \left(N_w, \left(\left\{ \frac{n_b m_{bw} s_w^{t-1} (1-s_w) r_w}{\sum_b n_b m_{bw}} : b \in \mathcal{B}, t \in \mathcal{T} \right\}, \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. 1 - \frac{\sum_{b,t} n_b m_{bw} s_w^{t-1} (1-s_w) r_w}{\sum_b n_b m_{bw}} \right) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Secondly, we condition on recovered individuals from the dataset in Eq. (A.1) and use the partial sum of the geometric series:

$$\{y_{bwt} : b \in \mathcal{W}, t \in \mathcal{T}\} \sim \operatorname{Multin} \left(y_w, \left\{ \frac{n_b m_{bw} s_w^{t-1} (1-s_w)}{\sum_b n_b m_{bw} (1-s_w^t)} : b \in \mathcal{B}, t \in \mathcal{T} \right\} \right). \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Finally, the data in Eq. (A.2) is aggregated according to the areas of origin resulting in

$$\{y_{wt} : t \in \mathcal{T}\} \sim \operatorname{Multin} \left(y_w, \left\{ \frac{s_w^{t-1} (1-s_w)}{1-s_w^t} : t \in \mathcal{T} \right\} \right). \quad (\text{A.3})$$

The relationship (A.3) only differs in t , and the probabilities equal the probability density of the geometric distribution truncated at time step T :

$$t_w \sim Geo^{tr}(1 - s_w, T),$$

where Geo^{tr} denotes the geometric distribution truncated at T .

The probability is

$$P(X = t | t \leq T) = \frac{s_w^{t-1} (1-s_w)}{1-s_w^T}.$$

So, estimating the survival probability in a specific destination area is possible by only considering the "age at death"-distribution of dead recoveries in that area.

The likelihood to maximize is

$$P_Y(s_w) = \prod_w \prod_t \left(\frac{s_w^{t-1} (1-s_w)}{1-s_w^t} \right)^{y_{wt}}.$$

Therefore, the logarithmic likelihood is

$$\log P_Y(s_w) = \sum_{w,t} (y_{wt}) ((t-1) \log s_w - \log(1-s_w^t) + \log(1-s_w)).$$

Appendix B. The uniqueness of the maximum likelihood estimator of survival

We prove the uniqueness of the solution for the MLE of s_w under certain conditions. A maximum of a function exists if the derivative of a function has a root and if the slope at the root is negative. It is unique, if there is exactly one such root. Therefore, we consider the partial derivative

$$\frac{\partial \log P_Y}{\partial s_w}(s_w) = \frac{\sum_t (y_{wt}(t-1))}{s_w} + \frac{y_w \cdot T s_w^{T-1}}{1-s_w^T} - \frac{y_w}{1-s_w}$$

and show that there is at most one root for such functions. Then, we discuss the conditions under which there is exactly one root.

Theorem 2. For all $a, b > 0, T > 1$ the function

$$s \mapsto \frac{a}{s} + b \left(\frac{T s^{T-1}}{1-s^T} - \frac{1}{1-s} \right)$$

has at most one root in $(0, 1)$.

A strictly monotonically decreasing function has at most one root. To prove [Theorem 2](#), we show in [Lemma 2](#) that the function multiplied by b is strictly monotonically decreasing. As a prerequisite we need the following inequality:

Lemma 1. For all $x > 0, T > 1$ the inequality

$$e^{Tx} - e^{-Tx} > T(e^x - e^{-x}) \tag{B.1}$$

holds.

Proof. As we know how e^x looks like, the function $f(x) = e^x - e^{-x}$ is strictly convex in $[0, \infty)$. Moreover, we choose $\lambda_1 = \frac{1}{T}$ and $\lambda_2 = \frac{T-1}{T}$. As $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = 1$, this fulfills the assumptions of Jensen's inequality saying that

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \lambda_i f(x_i) < f\left(\sum_{i=1}^2 \lambda_i x_i\right).$$

Now, we choose $x_1 = Tx$ and $x_2 = 0$ and insert it in Jensen's inequality:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{T}f(Tx) + \frac{T-1}{T}f(0) &> f(x) \\ \iff \frac{1}{T}(e^{Tx} - e^{-Tx}) + \frac{T-1}{T}0 &> e^x - e^{-x} \\ \iff e^{Tx} - e^{-Tx} &> T(e^x - e^{-x}). \end{aligned}$$

Now, we prove monotony using the inequality [Eq. B.1](#):

Lemma 2. For all $T > 1$ the function

$$g(s) = \frac{T s^T}{1-s^T} - \frac{s}{1-s}$$

is strictly monotonically decreasing in $[0, 1)$.

Proof. One has

$$\begin{aligned} g'(s) &= \frac{T^2 s^{T-1}}{(1-s^T)^2} - \frac{1}{(1-s)^2} \\ \iff -(1-s^T)^2(1-s)^2 g'(s) &= 1 - T^2 s^{T-1} + 2(T^2 - 1)s^T \\ &\quad - T^2 s^{T+1} + s^{2T}. \end{aligned}$$

Let $s \in (0, 1)$ be $s = e^{-2x}$ for $x = -\frac{1}{2} \ln s > 0$. It is a consequence of [Lemma 1](#) that

$$\begin{aligned} e^{Tx} - e^{-Tx} &> T(e^x - e^{-x}) > 0 \\ \iff (e^{Tx} - e^{-Tx})^2 &> T^2(e^x - e^{-x})^2 \\ \iff e^{2Tx} - 2 + e^{-2Tx} &> T^2 e^{2x} - 2T^2 + T^2 e^{-2x} \\ \iff \frac{1}{s^T} - 2 + s^T &> T^2 \frac{1}{s} - 2T^2 + T^2 s \\ \iff 1 - 2s^T + s^{2T} &> T^2 s^{T-1} - 2T^2 s^T + T^2 s^{T+1} \\ \iff 0 &< 1 - T^2 s^{T-1} + 2(T^2 - 1)s^T - T^2 s^{T+1} + s^{2T} \\ \iff 0 &< -(1-s^T)^2(1-s)^2 g'(s). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $g'(s) < 0$ and g is strictly monotonically decreasing.

Finally, we can prove [Theorem 2](#).

Proof. [Proof of [Theorem 2](#)] We assume that there exist $a, b > 0$ and $0 < s, \tilde{s} < 1$. If the function has a root, its value is 0 at the root. We start with two roots s and \tilde{s} :

$$\frac{a}{s} + b \left(\frac{T s^{T-1}}{1-s^T} - \frac{1}{1-s} \right) = 0 = \frac{a}{\tilde{s}} + b \left(\frac{T \tilde{s}^{T-1}}{1-\tilde{s}^T} - \frac{1}{1-\tilde{s}} \right).$$

It ensues immediately, that

$$s \left(\frac{T s^{T-1}}{1-s^T} - \frac{1}{1-s} \right) = -\frac{a}{b} = \tilde{s} \left(\frac{T \tilde{s}^{T-1}}{1-\tilde{s}^T} - \frac{1}{1-\tilde{s}} \right)$$

or

$$\frac{T s^T}{1-s^T} - \frac{s}{1-s} = \frac{T \tilde{s}^T}{1-\tilde{s}^T} - \frac{\tilde{s}}{1-\tilde{s}}.$$

[Lemma 2](#) shows that $s = \tilde{s}$ because $f(s) = f(\tilde{s})$ and the function is strictly monotonically decreasing. So, if there is a root, there is only one root.

From [Theorem 2](#) follows, that there exists at most one root for [Eq. \(5\)](#), when $s_w \in (0, 1)$. Now, we can consider for which conditions there is exactly one solution for $s_w \in (0, 1)$ and which values will be attained by \hat{s}_w .

Lemma 3. For all $a, b > 0$ and $T > 1$ the function

$$s \mapsto \frac{a}{s} + b \left(\frac{T s^{T-1}}{1-s^T} - \frac{1}{1-s} \right) \tag{2}$$

has

- (i) either exactly one root in $(0,1)$, if $a + \frac{b(1-T)}{2} \leq 0$. Then \hat{s} equals the root, or
- (ii) no root in $(0,1)$, if $a + \frac{b(1-T)}{2} > 0$. Then $\hat{s} = 1$.

Proof. As $a, b > 0$ and $T > 1$, it follows from [Theorem 2](#), that there is at most one root in $(0, 1)$ for [Eq. \(2\)](#). It remains to be shown in which case there is a conversion between the boundaries.

As $\frac{a}{s} \xrightarrow{s \rightarrow 0} +\infty$ and $b \left(\frac{T s^{T-1}}{1-s^T} - \frac{1}{1-s} \right) \xrightarrow{s \rightarrow 0} -b, g(s) \xrightarrow{s \rightarrow 0} +\infty$. So, the left boundary has a plus-sign.

Now, we investigate the limit for the right boundary:

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{s \rightarrow 1} \left(\frac{a}{s} + b \left(\frac{T s^{T-1}}{1-s^T} - \frac{1}{1-s} \right) \right) &= \lim_{s \rightarrow 1} \frac{a(1-s^T - s + s^{T+1}) + b(T s^T - T s^{T+1} - s + s^{T+1})}{s - s^{T+1} - s^2 + s^{T+2}} \\ &= \frac{0}{0}. \end{aligned}$$

Using l'Hôpital's rule, we obtain

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 1} \frac{\frac{a(1-s^{T-1} - s + s^{T+1}) + b(Ts^T - Ts^{T+1} - s + s^{T+1})}{\frac{a}{s}(s-s^{T+1} - s^2 + s^{T+2})}}{\frac{a(-Ts^{T-1} - 1 + (T+1)s^T) + b(T^2s^{T-1} - T(T+1)s^T - 1 + (T+1)s^T)}{1 - (T+1)s^T - 2s + (T+2)s^{T+1}}} = \lim_{s \rightarrow 1} \frac{a(-Ts^{T-1} - 1 + (T+1)s^T) + b(T^2s^{T-1} - T(T+1)s^T - 1 + (T+1)s^T)}{1 - (T+1)s^T - 2s + (T+2)s^{T+1}} = \frac{0}{0}.$$

So, we use l'Hôpital's rule again:

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 1} \frac{\frac{a(-Ts^{T-1} - 1 + (T+1)s^T) + b(T^2s^{T-1} - T(T+1)s^T - 1 + (T+1)s^T)}{\frac{a}{s}(1 - (T+1)s^T - 2s + (T+2)s^{T+1})}}{\frac{a(-T(T-1)s^{T-2} + T^2s^{T-1} + Ts^{T-1}) + b((T^3 - T^2)s^{T-2} - T^2s^{T-1} + Ts^{T-1})}{-T^2s^{T-1} - Ts^{T-1} - 2s + (T^2 + T)s^T + (2T+2)s^T}} = \lim_{s \rightarrow 1} \frac{a(-T(T-1)s^{T-2} + T^2s^{T-1} + Ts^{T-1}) + b((T^3 - T^2)s^{T-2} - T^2s^{T-1} + Ts^{T-1})}{-T^2s^{T-1} - Ts^{T-1} - 2s + (T^2 + T)s^T + (2T+2)s^T} = a + \frac{b(1-T)}{2}.$$

This expression will be less or equal than 0 if

$$a + \frac{b(1-T)}{2} \leq 0.$$

In this case there is a conversion between the boundaries. Exactly one root exists and the REML-estimator \hat{s} equals the root.

If

$$a + \frac{b(1-T)}{2} > 0,$$

there is no conversion between the boundaries and therefore no root exists. As a consequence of the positive value at the left boundary and [Theorem 2](#), we know that the derivative of the likelihood is positive without a root. Therefore, the likelihood increases strictly monotonically and has its maximum at 1, so $\hat{s} = 1$.

Appendix C. Monotonically decreasing data leads to a unique survival estimate

Lemma 4. For all $a = \sum_t (y_{wt}(t-1))$, $b = y_{w \cdot} \cdot y_{wt}$ monotonically decreasing in t , $T > 1$ the following inequality holds:

$$a + \frac{b(1-T)}{2} < 0.$$

Proof. One has

$$\begin{aligned} a + \frac{b(1-T)}{2} &= \sum_t (y_{wt}(t-1)) + \frac{1-T}{2} \sum_t y_{wt} < 0 \\ \iff \sum_t (y_{wt}(t-1 + \frac{1-T}{2})) &< 0 \\ \iff \sum_t (y_{wt}(t - \frac{1+T}{2})) &< 0. \end{aligned}$$

This inequality holds because there are T summands, from which $\lfloor \frac{T}{2} \rfloor$ are both positive and negative. The value is $t - \frac{T+1}{2}$ weighted by y_{wt} . As the positive and negative values have the same absolute value, but the weight decreases, the whole sum is negative.

Appendix D. A large enough sample size leads to monotonically decreasing data

Lemma 5. For all $a = \sum_t (y_{wt}(t-1))$, $b = y_{w \cdot}$, $P(a + \frac{b(1-T)}{2} > 0) \xrightarrow{N_{w \cdot} \rightarrow \infty} 0$.

Proof. Let $r_{N_{w \cdot}} = \frac{1}{N_{w \cdot}} y_{wt}$ be the relative frequency of individuals found in destination area w at time t and $\epsilon > 0$. Following the weak law of large numbers

$$\lim_{N_{w \cdot} \rightarrow \infty} P(|r_{N_{w \cdot}} - \mathbb{E}[r_{N_{w \cdot}}]| \geq \epsilon) = 0,$$

so,

$$r_{N_{w \cdot}} \xrightarrow{N_{w \cdot} \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}[r_{N_{w \cdot}}] = s_w^{T-1} (1 - s_w) r_w.$$

Because $s \in (0, 1)$ and

$$y_{bwt_1} \geq y_{bwt_2} \iff t_1 < t_2.$$

Therefore,

$$P\left(a + \frac{b(1-T)}{2} > 0\right) \xrightarrow{N_{w \cdot} \rightarrow \infty} 0$$

according to [Lemma 4](#).

Appendix E. A long enough observation time leads to a unique survival estimator

Lemma 6. If T is large, the time of the dead recoveries will be distributed by

$$t_w \sim \text{Geo}(1 - s_w).$$

The MLE of s is

$$\hat{s}_w = 1 - \frac{y_{w \cdot}}{\sum_t t y_{wt}}$$

Proof. As s_w is a probability, $s_w^T \rightarrow 0$ for $T \rightarrow \infty$, so $t \sim \text{Geom}(s_w)$, if T is large. For the geometric distribution, the MLE is

$$\hat{s}_w = 1 - \frac{y_{w \cdot}}{\sum_t t y_{wt}}$$

Appendix F. The latent count is a multiple of the dead recovery data

Lemma 7. Let $X_i \sim \text{Bin}(n, p)$, $i \in \{1, \dots, r\}$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Consider $p \in [0, 1]$ to be known. Then the unique MLE of the parameter n is

$$\hat{n} = \left\lceil \frac{\sum_{i=1}^r X_i}{1 - (1-p)^r} \right\rceil$$

Proof.

see e.g., [Feldman and Fox \(1968\)](#).

Theorem. Let $y_{bw \cdot} \sim \text{Bin}(n, p)$ with $n = N_{bw \cdot}$ and $p = (1 - s_w^T) r_w$ for a fixed $b \in \mathcal{B}$ and a fixed $w \in \mathcal{H}$. For all $b \in \mathcal{B}$ and all $w \in \mathcal{H}$ holds

$$\hat{N}_{bw \cdot} = \lfloor \lambda_w y_{bw \cdot} \rfloor, \quad \lambda_w \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Proof. As $y_{bw \cdot} \sim \text{Bin}(N_{bw \cdot}, (1 - s_w^T) r_w)$, we can assume that $p_w = (1 - s_w^T) r_w$ is a fixed value in $[0, 1]$. According to [Lemma 7](#) the MLE of $N_{bw \cdot}$ is

$$\hat{N}_{bw} = \left[\frac{y_{bw}}{1 - (1 - p_w)^T} \right] = \left[\frac{y_{bw}}{p_w} \right].$$

So, if $\lambda_w = \frac{1}{p_w} = \frac{1}{(1 - s_w^T)r_w}$, $\hat{N}_{bw} = \lfloor \lambda_w y_{bw} \rfloor$.

Appendix G. The formula of the scaling factor

Theorem 4. If $\forall b \in \mathcal{B} : N_{bw} = \lfloor \lambda_w y_{bw} \rfloor, \lambda_w \in \mathbb{R}, w \in \mathcal{W}, B \geq W$, then $\lambda_w = \frac{\det \mathbf{Y}_w^{(N)}}{\det \mathbf{Y}}$.

Proof. Let e_w be the w -th vector of the standard basis. As is widely known, the determinant is a standardized multilinear alternating form, see e.g., Knabner and Barth (2017).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\det \mathbf{Y}_w^{(N)}}{\det \mathbf{Y}} &= \frac{\det (y_1 \dots y_{w-1} N_{bw} y_{w+1} \dots y_W)}{\det \mathbf{Y}} = \frac{1}{\det \mathbf{Y}} \det \left(y_1, \dots, y_{w-1}, N_{bw} + \sum_{\substack{\tilde{w} \in \mathcal{W}, \\ \tilde{w} \neq w}} \lambda_{\tilde{w}} y_{\tilde{w}} y_{w+1}, \dots, y_W \right) \\ &= \frac{\det (y_1 \dots y_{w-1} N_{bw} y_{w+1} \dots y_W)}{\det \mathbf{Y}} \det \left(e_1, \dots, e_{w-1}, \sum_{\substack{\tilde{w} \in \mathcal{W}, \\ \tilde{w} \neq w}} \lambda_{\tilde{w}} e_{\tilde{w}} + e_w, e_{w+1}, \dots, e_W \right) \\ &= \frac{\det (y_1 \dots y_{w-1} N_{bw} y_{w+1} \dots y_W)}{\det \mathbf{Y}} \left(\det \mathbf{I}_w + \sum_{\substack{\tilde{w} \in \mathcal{W}, \\ \tilde{w} \neq w}} \det (e_1, \dots, e_{w-1}, \lambda_{\tilde{w}} e_{\tilde{w}}, e_{w+1}, \dots, e_W) \right) \\ &= \frac{\det (y_1 \dots y_{w-1} N_{bw} y_{w+1} \dots y_W)}{\det \mathbf{Y}} \det (\mathbf{I}_w) = \frac{\det (y_1 \dots y_{w-1} N_{bw} y_{w+1} \dots y_W)}{\det \mathbf{Y}} \\ &= \frac{\det (y_1 \dots y_{w-1} \lambda_w y_w y_{w+1} \dots y_W)}{\det \mathbf{Y}} = \lambda_w \frac{\det (y_1 \dots y_{w-1} y_w y_{w+1} \dots y_W)}{\det \mathbf{Y}} = \lambda_w \frac{\det \mathbf{Y}}{\det \mathbf{Y}} = \lambda_w \end{aligned}$$

Appendix H. The distribution of the latent count and the maximum likelihood estimator of migratory connectivity

Theorem 4. The distribution of the number of individuals of one area of origin in different destination areas can be described as

$$\{N_{bw} : w \in \mathcal{W}\} \sim \text{Multin}(N_{b..}, \{m_{bw} : w \in \mathcal{W}\}).$$

The MLE for the proportion of individuals from the population of origin b going to destination area w is

$$\hat{m}_{bw} = \frac{y_{bw} \cdot \det \mathbf{Y}_w^{(N)}}{N_{b..} \cdot \det \mathbf{Y}}.$$

Proof. We start with the overall multinomial distribution of the data (1). Aggregating over all time steps t results in tuples of found and not found individuals for every combination of area of origin and destination area:

$$\{(y_{bw}, (N_{bw} - y_{bw})) : b \in \mathcal{B}, w \in \mathcal{W}\} \sim \text{Multin}(N_{...}, \{(n_b m_{bw} (1 - s_w^T)r_w) (n_b m_{bw} - n_b m_{bw} (1 - s_w^T)r_w) : b \in \mathcal{B}, w \in \mathcal{W}\}).$$

By aggregating the found and the not found individuals in the relationship 2 we obtain

$$\{N_{bw} : b \in \mathcal{B}, w \in \mathcal{W}\} \sim \text{Multin}(N_{...}, \{n_b m_{bw} : b \in \mathcal{B}, w \in \mathcal{W}\}).$$

Finally, we condition on the area of origin, so for every area of origin b

$$\{N_{bw} : w \in \mathcal{W}\} \sim \text{Multin}(N_{b..}, \{m_{bw} : w \in \mathcal{W}\}).$$

According to Eq. (3) and Theorem 3 the MLE is

$$\hat{m}_{bw} = \frac{\hat{N}_{bw}}{N_{b..}} = \frac{y_{bw} \cdot \det \mathbf{Y}_w^{(N)}}{N_{b..} \cdot \det \mathbf{Y}}.$$

Appendix I. The maximum likelihood estimator of recovery probability

Theorem 5. The data is distributed by

$$(y_{.w}, (N_{.w} - y_{.w})) \sim \text{Multin}(N_{.w}, ((1 - s_w^T)r_w \mathbf{1} - (1 - s_w^T)r_w)).$$

The destination area-specific recovery probability can be estimated by

$$\hat{r}_w = \frac{\det \mathbf{Y}}{(1 - \hat{s}_w^T) \det \mathbf{Y}_w^{(N)}}.$$

Proof. Starting with the relationship (A.1), we aggregate the data of all areas of origin and time steps. Using the partial sum of the geometric series, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} (y_{.w}, (N_{.w} - y_{.w})) \\ \sim \text{Multin} \left(N_{.w}, \left(\frac{\sum_{b,t} n_b m_{bw} s_w^{t-1} (1 - s_w)r_w}{\sum_b n_b m_{bw}} \mathbf{1} - \frac{\sum_{b,t} n_b m_{bw} s_w^{t-1} (1 - s_w)r_w}{\sum_b n_b m_{bw}} \right) \right) \\ = \text{Multin}(N_{.w}, ((1 - s_w^T)r_w \mathbf{1} - (1 - s_w^T)r_w)). \end{aligned}$$

According to Eq. (3) and Theorem 3 the MLE is

$$(1 - \hat{s}_w^T)r_w = \frac{y_{.w}}{N_{.w}} = \frac{y_{.w}}{\sum_b \hat{N}_{bw}}.$$

As s_w can be estimated as \hat{s}_w by Theorem 1, the recovery probability can be estimated as

$$\hat{r}_w = \frac{y_{.w}}{(1 - \hat{s}_w^T) \sum_b \hat{N}_{bw}} = \frac{y_{.w}}{(1 - \hat{s}_w^T) \sum_b y_{bw} \cdot \frac{\det \mathbf{Y}_w^{(N)}}{\det \mathbf{Y}}} = \frac{\det \mathbf{Y}}{(1 - \hat{s}_w^T) \det \mathbf{Y}_w^{(N)}}$$

Appendix J. Potential non-breeding area of robins ringed at the Greifswalder Oie

The potential non-breeding area of robins ringed at the Greifswalder Oie is shown in Fig. J.8.

Fig. J.8. Location of all dead recoveries and live resightings of robins ringed during fall migration at the Greifswalder Oie, Northern Germany. Discrete destination areas are indicated by shading: dark: North, medium: Central, light: South.

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